

ACTIVITIES OF THE PEOPLES LIVING IN THE KOKAND KHANATE

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Annotation

This article studies the occupations of the peoples living in the territory of the Kokand Khanate. Also, each occupation is described separately and its specific features are revealed.

Keywords: sedentary, nomadic, semi-nomadic, livestock breeding, farming, gardening, viticulture, crafts, handicrafts.

At the end of the 18th century, the territories of the khanate still consisted of the Fergana Valley. The valley is located in a favorable climate and natural geographical region, its area is 22.2 thousand km, including mountainous areas - 80 thousand km, its length from east to west is 300 km, and from north to south sometimes 170 km. The population of the territories included in the Khanate differed in their location and lifestyle. The Tashkent oasis and the irrigated part of the Fergana Valley were densely populated and led a sedentary lifestyle, while the desert, mountain, and foothill plains were inhabited by nomadic and semi-nomadic people.

The settled population was more numerous than the nomadic and semi-nomadic population. At the beginning of the 19th century, more than 40 percent of the population were nomads and semi-nomadic, while by the end of the century they accounted for 15 percent. According to economic activities, the main part of the settled population was engaged in agriculture, crafts and trade, while the nomadic and semi-nomadic population was engaged in animal husbandry. Most of the agricultural crops in the khanate were typical of the Central Asian khanates, and grain growing, gardening, vegetable and melon growing, and sericulture were well developed. Of the grain crops, corn was widely grown, which was the main consumer product of the poor in cities and villages and was considered cattle feed. By the 19th century, the khanate began to pay great attention to cotton cultivation, and the area under this crop was constantly expanding.

The natural conditions of the western part of the valley were very favorable for the development of horticulture and viticulture. The southwestern regions of Khujand, Konibodom, Isfara, Sokh, Chimyan, Rishton, were mainly specialized in apricot cultivation. During this period, mulberry trees were widespread throughout the Fergana Valley, and they had long been cultivated for silk

production in the foothills and ancient agricultural oases of Sokh, Isfara, Namangan, and Asht.

The mountainous regions, mountain slopes, and hills of the Fergana Valley were effectively used by nomadic and semi-nomadic populations for wintering and grazing. At the same time, these areas were suitable for spring and autumn grazing.

The poor peasants of the Kokand Khanate were even exploited by small traders, and the middle and lower classes practically did not eat meat.

In the handicraft industry, even the production of one type or part of a product, crafts and artisanship played an important role in the economic life of the urban population of the Kokand Khanate. The crafts of the Kokand Khanate, which had a long history of development, were highly specialized. This can be especially observed in weaving and blacksmithing. Craftsmen were skilled craftsmen who had mastered the secrets of their profession and were able to raise the products they produced to the level of high art. Craftsmen tried to ensure that the quality of their products was high. However, fierce competition in the market prompted them to keep the secrets of their profession secret. The subtleties of professions were taught only to their children, and sometimes to their apprentices, and in this way they were passed down from generation to generation.

In the Kokand Khanate, the capital of the country and all other cities. The main part of the population was engaged in crafts and trades. Neighborhoods had special workshops, teams and shops depending on their specialized craft. This can also be seen from the names of neighborhoods and streets in cities. Although the development of crafts was the same in almost all cities and villages of the country, production was distinguished by its certain characteristics, namely the type and quality of products. Blacksmithing, jewelry, weaving, pottery, coppersmithing and other branches of crafts were widely developed, and each city of the khanate became famous for the products it produced in a certain field. In particular, the city of Kokand was famous for jewelry and paper production, Shahriksan and Chust for sewing and iron processing, in particular for knife making, Margilan, Namangan and Andijan for silk weaving, Tashkent for sewing, cast iron, iron and copper products. Notable areas of Khanate craftsmanship include Namangan, The cities of Kokand and Margilan produced satin, silk, adras and bekasam fabrics. Masters produced very high-quality products in most cities, especially in Kokand. There were many experienced masters in Kokand, who, having raised their products to the level of art, had

regular customers and clients. This indicates that the craftsmen were constantly provided with work.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the city of Kokand, production was also based on manual labor, and the main types of crafts were weaving yarn and silk fabrics, making shoes, leatherworking, making pottery, blacksmithing, saddlery, painting, coppersmithing, jewelry, carpentry, cart building, military weapons production, carving, wax work, charcoal production, embroidery, skull making, roofing, and the like. There were also gunpowder and papermaking workshops belonging to the khan.

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